

SYNTHESIS OF A (WSi₂, W₅Si₃)-SiC COMPOSITE USING THE REACTION BETWEEN WC AND Si

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SUMMARY: This paper reports a study on the formation of tungsten and molybdenum silicides by displacement reaction between Si-WC, and Si-Mo₂C respectively at temperatures ranging from 1300°C to 1900°C. The preparation variables have been the ratio metallic carbide to silicon ratio in order to control the type of silicide formed, and the W/Mo ratio, in order to synthesise the mixed silicide. The synthesis of different silicides takes place at different temperatures; however, it is necessary to increase the temperature to 1900°C for the synthesis of W₅Si₃. The Vickers hardness of the silicides increases with the mixture of both silicides (MSi₂, M₅Si₃), in the mixed silicides (Mo,W)Si₂ the best results are obtained, when the (Mo/W) ratio is 3/1. In this case, the value is 16.5 GPa, and the fracture toughness for the same material is 8MPa·m^{1/2}.

KEYWORDS: WSi₂, MoSi₂, (WSi₂, W₅Si₃)-SiC, (Mo/W) Si₂- SiC, WC, Mo₂C.

INTRODUCTION

Silicides have attracted the attention of researchers due to a combination of interesting properties. The low electrical resistivity of silicides together with high thermal stability, electromigration resistance and excellent diffusion-barrier characteristics is important for microelectronic applications. Additionally, silicides also possess the necessary attributes for a high-temperature structural material, including a high melting point, low density, excellent oxidation resistance, and good mechanical and microstructural stability from room temperature to the service temperature. Potential high-temperature applications include turbine airfoils, burning chamber parts, and missile nozzles [1].

Conventionally, silicides are processed either by arc melting, silicidation of elemental powders, or reduction of the metal oxide. These processes are energy-intensive and require long homogenization times in order to obtain the desired products. The loss of silicon by volatilization during arc melting can result in the formation of undesirable intermediate phases. In addition, the silicide powders obtained by these routes have high oxygen contents and other impurities, which are unacceptable for high temperature structural applications and also in the fabrication of microelectronics devices. By using reactive processing techniques such as combustion synthesis, mechanical alloying, chemical vapor deposition, plasma vapor deposition and displacement reactions, high-purity powders can be obtained [1].

Most transition metal silicides have ordered structures up to their melting points and very narrow composition ranges. The highest oxidation resistance is found for the higher silicon compounds, the disilicides. Plastic deformation is limited in MoSi₂ and WSi₂ structures and only becomes significant at high temperatures, above the brittle-to-ductile transition temperature [2].

MoSi₂ seems to be one of the most promising disilicide for high-temperature applications owing to its excellent oxidation and corrosion resistance, high electrical and thermal conductivity, reasonably low density (6.31 g·cm⁻³) and high melting point (2020 °C) [2]. It is perhaps the best characterised one due to its previous use in non-structural applications such as heating elements and certain electronic applications. Tungsten disilicid could be another interesting material because of its high melting point (2160 °C). Its use in structural applications, however, is plagued by a low fracture toughness at room temperature and low strength at elevated temperatures, as well as a pesting behavior at intermediate temperatures [3]. One way to improve the strength at elevated temperature and creep resistance of MoSi₂ and WSi₂ is to prepare a composite with SiC particles or whiskers.

While powder processing appears to be the preferred route for preparing most silicides, it is difficult to avoid the incorporation of substantial amounts of an amorphous silica phase during consolidation. After consolidation, this amorphous silica phase exists as discrete particles which are suspected to be detrimental to the mechanical properties by serving as potential crack nucleation sites that, ultimately, degrade the strength at room temperature and toughness. The properties at elevated temperature may also be degraded by silica because of its relatively low softening temperature (~1250 °C) [3]. To avoid this problem, this material must be prepared *in situ*. Solid state displacement reactions are being evaluated as a route to produce intermetallic/ceramic matrix composites *in situ*. Solid state displacement reactions are diffusional phase transformations whereby two or more elements or compounds react to form new compounds that are more stable thermodynamically than the starting reactants. Interwoven or dispersed microstructures, which are very important for the strength and the toughness of the composite, and can not be obtained by other methods, are easily achieved by using displacement reactions. This amounts to growing the reinforcement phases *in situ*, which is becoming an increasingly important concept in composite synthesis. Control of the morphology of the product phases is a critical aspect of these methods. Issues of microstructural control and cleanliness can be addressed using displacement reactions in ways that cannot be achieved with other techniques [4].

Previous work on the MoSi₂/SiC system obtained from Mo₂C and SiC by means of a solid-state reaction within blended powder compacts had shown that the “stoichiometric” reaction $\text{Mo}_2\text{C} + 5 \text{Si} = 2 \text{MoSi}_2 + \text{SiC}$ yielded a potentially useful composite material [5]. The aim of this work is to analyse the possibility of manufacturing multiphase composite materials based on the Mo/W- Si-C system, in order to increase the mechanical properties of MoSi₂-derived materials, using a solid state displacement reaction between Mo₂C, WC and Si.

EXPERIMENTAL

The starting powders were silicon (purity 99%, particle size 36 μm), WC (purity 99%, particle size 36 μm) and Mo₂C (purity 99%, particle size 36 μm), supplied by ALDRICH. Two different kind of reactions were studied: the reaction between WC and silicon, and the reaction between WC, Mo₂C and silicon. In the first one, three different types of mixtures were made by modifying the proportions of the two reactants in order to obtain three different

composites: WSi_2/SiC , W_5Si_3/SiC and $(WSi_2, W_5Si_3)/SiC$. In the second one, three different types of mixtures were also made by modifying the proportions of the reactants in order to obtain three different composites: $(W_{0.5}, Mo_{0.5})Si_2/SiC$, $(W_{0.75}, Mo_{0.25})Si_2/SiC$ and $(W_{0.25}, Mo_{0.75})Si_2/SiC$.

The mixture of the powders was made in an ethanolic solution using an automatic stirrer at low temperature. The solvent was evaporated after two or three hours and the resulting slurry was dried at 110 °C and pelletized under vacuum in a die at 40°C. Heat treatment of the preforms was carried out in a horizontal furnace at 1300 or 1450 °C, under a flow of 90 ml/min of argon with a soaking time of 10 hours and 30 min, respectively. The determination of the SiC, $MoSi_2$ and Mo_5Si_3 formed was carried out by X-ray diffraction (JSD Debye-Flex 2002 from Seifert) fitted with a Cu cathode and a Ni filter and using a 2 °/min scanning rate. The morphology of the product was analyzed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (JSM 840, from JEOL) fitted with a Link QK 200 dispersive X-ray analyzer, and by Reflecting Polarized-light Microscopy (Leica). Microhardness was determined by use of the indentation method with a Vickers hardness tester, with a load of 4.9 and 9.8 N for 15 s. Indentation was measured using an optical head equipped with a vernier scale giving a potential accuracy in the measurements of $\pm 0.25 \mu m$.

Disks were prepared using the same initial mixtures (each one was made with 25g of the mixture), but employing a vacuum hot pressing process. Each one of the three different types of mixtures was pressed during 1 hour at 1700 and 1900°C. These pieces were analyzed by X-Ray diffraction, optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. Microhardness was determined with a Vickers hardness tester.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a) Reaction between WC and silicon.

The two possible reactions taking place during the synthesis are:

Table 1 shows the mass fraction of products formed, after reaction at 1300 and 1450°C for mixtures with different Si/WC molar ratio. Theoretically, type 1 mixtures should produce WSi_2 as the only silicide, type 3 samples should produce W_5Si_3 and type 2 mixtures should produce both silicides. In practice, W_5Si_3 was not detected in any sample prepared with powders. These results are different from those obtained when employing Mo_2C , where both silicides were obtained [6].

Table 1.- Experimental mass fraction of silicides after reaction at 1300 and 1450°C.

		1300 °C			
Mixture	Si/WC Molar ratio	WSi_2	WC	SiC	Others
1	3.0	0.66	0.23	0.11	----
2	2.3	0.58	0.33	0.09	----
3	1.6	0.48	0.44	0.08	Si
		1450 °C			
1	3.0	0.86	0.00	0.14	----
2	2.3	0.70	0.18	0.12	----
3	1.6	0.54	0.37	0.09	Si

Table 2 shows the experimental results obtained at 1700 and 1900°C for the three types of mixtures. These results are similar to those obtained at the lower temperatures, and W_5Si_2 is only appreciably at 1900°C, but in a lower amount to that theoretically expected.

Table 2.- Experimental mass fraction of silicides after reaction at 1700 and 1900°C.

Mixture	Si/WC Molar ratio	1700 °C			
		WSi ₂	WC	SiC	Others
1	3.0	0.86	0.00	0.14	----
2	2.3	0.67	0.17	0.12	W ₅ Si ₃
3	1.6	0.50	0.35	0.09	W ₅ Si ₃
		1900 °C			
1	3.0	0.86	0.00	0.14	----
2	2.3	0.50	0.13	0.11	W ₅ Si ₃
3	1.6	0.35	0.25	0.10	W ₅ Si ₃

Hojo *et al.* [7-8] claim that it is easier to obtain Mo_5Si_3 in the Si-Mo-C system because it has a lower free energy of formation than $MoSi_2$, whereas it is higher for W_5Si_3 than for WSi_2 in the Si-W-C system. Following their data, it could be concluded that it would be impossible to form $MoSi_2$ in the Si-Mo-C system and W_5Si_3 in the Si-W-C system, but they are indeed formed. However, it can be obtained, from a more exhaustive analysis, that it is thermodynamically feasible to obtain $MoSi_2$ from silicon and Mo_5Si_3 . It is not so evident in the Si-W-C system, because now WC has to react with Wsi_2 to produce W_5Si_3 and SiC. Both reactants are solids and the reaction is very slow; therefore, the reaction temperature has to be close to the melting point of the products in order the reaction rate to be acceptable.

The analysis of the pieces shows:

- Mixtures type 1: very homogenous distribution of SiC on the matrix of WSi_2 ; at 1700 °C a very little quantity of W_5Si_3 was detected and, at 1900°C, SiC was observed in the boundary of W_5Si_3 particles
- Mixtures type 2: the two silicides were formed and there was a lot of SiC in the boundary of W_5Si_3 particles. .
- Mixtures type 3: at 1700°C the reaction was not complete, and only a little amount of WSi_2 was formed (probably the temperature was too low); at 1900 °C pieces exhibit great homogeneity, and the two silicides were identified.

Figure. 1 Micrograph of a WSi_2 - W_5Si_3 -SiC piece. Three different phases can be observed: W_5Si_3 (light grey), WSi_2 (dark grey) and SiC (black).

Table 3 reports the microhardness of the different pieces. It can be seen that WSi₂ prepared at 1700 °C shows already good mechanical properties but, in the other cases, it is necessary to use high temperatures to complete the sintering process. When this is achieved, better properties are obtained. Same results were found in the Mo-Si-C system.

Table 3. Microhardness of the different samples at the treatment temperatures.

Temperature	Microhardness (GPa)		
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
1700	14.4	7.3	-----
1900	14.5	15	16.0

b) Reaction between WC, Mo₂C and silicon:

The three reactions taking place during the synthesis are:

Table 4 shows the experimental results obtained at 1300 and 1450°C for three types of mixtures (*type 1: (1/4W,3/4Mo)*; *type 2: (1/2W,1/2Mo)*; *type 3: (3/4W,1/4Mo)*). It can be seen that the mixed silicide is obtained in all cases. Also, the reaction is more favoured than for WSi₂ (table 1, sample 1).

Table 4.- Experimental mass fraction of silicides after reaction at 1300 and 1450°C, for mixtures type 1 to 3.

		1300 °C			
Mixture	Mo/W Molar ratio	(Mo,W)Si ₂	WC	SiC	Others
1	3/1	0.82	0.02	0.10	Si
2	2/2	0.80	0.03	0.11	Si
3	1/3	0.80	0.03	0.12	Si
		1450 °C			
1	3/1	0.87	0.00	0.12	----
2	2/2	0.85	0.00	0.14	----
3	1/3	0.85	0.00	0.15	----

The analysis of the disks shows that when the W content increases the porosity of the system and the distribution of the different phases become very homogeneous. Also, when the temperature increases the porosity decreases. Sample 1 shows an increment of grain size when the temperature increases. Hojo *et al.* [8] obtained similar results when sintered at 1700°C mixtures of (Mo,W)Si₂ obtained by displacement reactions similar to those presented here. Their pieces has a low porosity, with a very homogeneous structure, but they only analyze the case in which both metals are in the same amount. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the microhardness as a function of the W content for both temperatures. It can be clearly seen that for the monometallic silicides, temperature does not affect the microhardness, it does affect in the case of mixed disilicides.

Microhardness evolution does not follow the mixing rules. For the three studied cases, microhardness is higher than the monometallic disilicides (WSi₂ and MoSi₂). Also, microhardness increases as the W content decreases. Ito *et al.* [9] have studied the (Mo, W)Si₂ system by preparing simple crystals by the directional solidification technique. They

found that WSi_2 is harder than MoSi_2 and explained it on the basis of a greater amount of pilling defects in the tungsten compound, this hindering the shift of planes. They also found that mixtures are much harder than expected, but they did not give any explanation to this observation.

Figure 2. Evolution of the microhardness as a function of the W content for 1700 and 1900°C.

Indentation fracture toughness (IFT) tests were also performed. The cracks used for the IFT measurements were the traces of median/radial cracks which propagated from the corners of high load (9.81 N) Vickers indentations. The IFT expression of Anstis et al. [10] was used to obtain values of K_{IC} . Fracture toughness does not present a direct ratio with the different parameters studied in this work, mainly due to the heterogeneity of the mixtures. Fracture toughness presents values between 6 and 9 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, but the highest values have been obtained with the mixtures treated at the highest temperature. Crack interactions with the SiC particles, such as crack deflection and crack-wake bridging, were observed. The fracture toughness for these composite materials is two times higher than that reported for monolithic MoSi_2 [11], and is very similar to the data reported earlier [12] for hot pressed MoSi_2/SiC (whiskers) composites.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded from this work that,

- a) It is possible to synthesize WSi_2 by displacement reactions from WC and Si.
- b) W_5Si_3 can also be synthesized by this route at much higher temperatures.
- c) The mechanical properties increase in the mixed silicides and in the composites with both metals.

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